

Original Research

Sustainability Reporting and Earnings Management: Evidence from State-Owned Firms of an Emerging Economy

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management in the context of state-owned manufacturing enterprises (SOEs) in Bangladesh, an emerging economy where governance structures and reporting practices remain under significant scrutiny. Using panel data from 17 manufacturing SOEs listed in Bangladesh for the period 2018–2023, this study applies a content analysis approach based on Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) standards to construct a sustainability reporting index. Earnings management is measured through discretionary accruals, while several board and firm-specific variables are controlled for in the analysis. Both OLS and Fixed Effects models have been used to test the hypothesis. Initial findings show an increasing trend in sustainability reporting by the SOEs. The regression results reveal that sustainability reporting significantly affects earnings management, though the direction of the association is mixed across contexts. Consistent with legitimacy theory, greater sustainability disclosure is found to reduce incentives for earnings manipulation by enhancing transparency and stakeholder trust. These findings contribute to the growing literature on sustainability disclosure in developing economies by highlighting the dual role of sustainability reporting in curbing and, at times, facilitating earnings management. The study provides practical insights for regulators, policymakers, and managers aiming to strengthen accountability and foster sustainable governance in Bangladesh's state-owned enterprise sector.

Keywords: Bangladesh, earnings management, emerging economy, state-owned enterprises, sustainability reporting.

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Introduction

Financial reporting is fundamental to corporate transparency, enabling investors, regulators, creditors, and policymakers to assess organizational performance and make informed decisions. Over the last decade, however, corporate disclosure has evolved beyond financial metrics to incorporate broader environmental, social, and governance (ESG) dimensions. Sustainability reporting has emerged as a key instrument in this regard, offering stakeholders a more comprehensive view of a firm's accountability, long-term value creation, and alignment with societal expectations (Mnif Sellami et al., 2019). Although such disclosures are expected to enhance transparency, they coexist with the persistent challenge of earnings management. It includes managerial attempts to adjust reported earnings to meet strategic, regulatory, or political objectives, thereby potentially undermining the credibility of corporate reports.

The relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management has attracted growing scholarly attention, yet empirical findings remain mixed. Some studies document that extensive sustainability disclosure constrains earnings manipulation by strengthening transparency and stakeholder scrutiny. Conversely, others highlight its potential misuse as a legitimacy device or symbolic tool to mask underlying financial irregularities (Onoja et al., 2021). This theoretical ambiguity is particularly salient in emerging economies, where institutional pressures, weak enforcement, and political influences may shape both sustainability practices and financial reporting behavior. The question of whether sustainability reporting genuinely improves reporting quality or serves as an opportunistic façade therefore remains open.

State-owned enterprises (SOEs) represent a unique institutional setting for examining this relationship. Unlike private firms, SOEs operate under dual mandates: achieving financial performance targets while fulfilling public policy objectives. International evidence from countries such as China, India, and Indonesia show that SOEs often face political interference, soft budget constraints, and varying governance structures that can influence reporting incentives, including both sustainability disclosure and earnings management. Despite this growing body of research, the literature remains dominated by broader emerging-market studies and provides limited nuanced insight into how sustainability reporting functions within SOE environments characterized by complex political, social, and governance dynamics.

Bangladesh presents an important yet underexplored setting in this regard. SOEs contribute significantly to national economic activity and play a strategic role in public service delivery. However, they also grapple with bureaucratic rigidities, performance pressure, and weak oversight mechanisms, conditions that can create incentives for earnings manipulation (Khan, 2021). At the same time, Bangladesh's sustainability reporting landscape is evolving, shaped by regulatory encouragement, stakeholder expectations, and the country's commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Vision 2041. These institutional features make Bangladeshi SOEs a compelling context for examining whether sustainability reporting curbs or coexists with earnings management.

Notwithstanding the global interest in the subject, empirical evidence on the sustainability reporting–earnings management nexus in Bangladesh remains scarce. Existing studies primarily focus on private listed firms, governance mechanisms, or traditional CSR disclosures, while SOEs have received limited systematic attention. Moreover, prior research has not sufficiently explored whether contextual factors commonly associated with SOEs, such as political influence, subsidy dependence, or operational mandates, shape the relationship between non-financial disclosure and earnings quality. Understanding these dynamics is essential, as the institutional vulnerabilities of SOEs may uniquely influence whether sustainability reporting functions as a transparency-enhancing mechanism or as a symbolic tool.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management in Bangladesh’s manufacturing state-owned enterprises (SOEs). Specifically, the study seeks to determine whether sustainability reporting acts as a deterrent to earnings manipulation or, conversely, serves as a strategic tool to mask opportunistic financial practices. In doing so, it also aims to assess whether external factors, when considered alongside sustainability reporting, have a significant influence on earnings management behaviors. By addressing these questions, the research intends to provide a nuanced understanding of how non-financial disclosure practices interact with financial reporting quality in a strategically important yet governance-challenged sector of the Bangladeshi economy. This study contributes to this literature by examining the association between sustainability reporting and earnings management in Bangladeshi manufacturing SOEs. Rather than claiming a fundamentally new theoretical mechanism, the study is positioned as a contextual replication that extends existing evidence to an underexamined institutional environment characterized by strong political oversight and governance constraints. By focusing on SOEs, the study provides insights into how sustainability disclosure operates within organizations that face competing pressures and mixed accountability structures.

This research contributes to the literature and practice in several ways. First, it provides the first empirical evidence on the sustainability reporting–earnings management relationship specifically within Bangladeshi SOEs. It enriches the emerging literature on public-sector corporate behavior in developing economies. Second, it responds to recent calls for context-sensitive replications by examining whether established findings from other emerging markets hold in a more politically embedded and institutionally constrained setting. Third, the analysis carries policy relevance by aligning with Bangladesh’s SDG commitments and Vision 2041 agenda and offers insights that may guide regulators and policymakers in strengthening disclosure frameworks and enhancing governance effectiveness in the state-owned sector. From a practical perspective, the findings have the potential to inform governance reforms in the state-owned sector, guiding policymakers and regulators in developing reporting frameworks and monitoring mechanisms that promote transparency, accountability, and alignment between financial performance and sustainability objectives. This is particularly relevant as Bangladesh continues its journey toward achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) while maintaining economic growth and industrial competitiveness.

Rest of the study is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the theoretical framework of the study. Section 3 discusses the prior literatures and develops hypothesis based on

prior findings. Section 4 demonstrates the sample and data section, variable definition and research model of the study. Section 5 presents the findings of the study whereas Section 6 discusses the findings in details. Finally, Section 7 draws the conclusion of the study and highlights the practical implications, limitations and area for future research.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory conceptualizes the firm as a nexus of contractual relationships between principals and agents, where goal misalignment and information asymmetry may incentivize managers to pursue private benefits (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Earnings management constitutes a classic manifestation of agency conflict, enabling managers to manipulate performance indicators to secure personal gains, meet targets, or avoid political or regulatory scrutiny (Zogning, 2017). Sustainability reporting has been presented in prior literature as a transparency-enhancing mechanism that can mitigate these conflicts by increasing the visibility of managerial actions and providing stakeholders with additional non-financial information that improves monitoring effectiveness (Ullah, 2018). By reducing opacity, sustainability reporting may constrain opportunities for earnings manipulation and encourage more long-term, stewardship-oriented behavior.

In the SOE context, agency problems are often amplified. The government, as the dominant or sole principal, may impose non-commercial objectives on SOEs, such as employment generation, price stabilization, or service delivery, which complicate performance evaluation and widen the scope for earnings manipulation. Political interference, weak performance-based incentives, and complex accountability structures may heighten agency costs relative to private firms. Thus, substantive sustainability reporting could help reduce entrenched information asymmetry by providing a broader set of indicators through which the government and other stakeholders evaluate SOE performance.

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory posits that organizations rely on societal acceptance to operate effectively; thus, they engage in disclosure practices that demonstrate alignment with social norms, environmental expectations, and community values (Deegan, 2002; Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975). Sustainability reporting functions as a legitimacy-seeking tool, enabling firms to signal commitment to social and environmental responsibilities (Fernando & Lawrence, 2014; Trisnawati et al., 2016). Under this framework, firms (particularly those subject to public scrutiny) may adopt comprehensive ESG disclosures to maintain or restore legitimacy.

SOEs are uniquely legitimacy-dependent. As publicly funded and politically visible organizations, they face heightened expectations of accountability, stewardship, and alignment with national development priorities. Failures in transparency or governance can generate reputational consequences not only for the enterprise but also for the government. Therefore, sustainability reporting may serve as a crucial legitimacy

mechanism for SOEs, reinforcing public trust and demonstrating adherence to societal mandates.

Stakeholder Theory and Institutional Theory

While agency and legitimacy theories explain managerial incentives and societal expectations, they are insufficient to capture the complex stakeholder and institutional pressures that shape SOE disclosure behavior. Stakeholder theory suggests that organizations respond to the demands of diverse groups (government, regulators, employees, civil society, creditors, development partners), each exerting influence over disclosure priorities. For SOEs, stakeholder pressure is multifaceted: political authorities seek enhanced transparency, regulators emphasize compliance, communities expect environmental responsibility, and international development agencies promote sustainability alignment. These pressures jointly increase the strategic relevance of sustainability reporting.

Institutional theory further underscores that organizational practices reflect broader institutional logics and coercive, normative, and mimetic pressures (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). SOEs in emerging economies often operate under evolving regulatory environments, strong political oversight, and increasing global expectations regarding sustainability. These institutional forces may encourage SOEs to adopt sustainability reporting practices not only for transparency but also to conform to regulatory and normative pressures tied to SDGs, donor expectations, and national development plans. Within such institutional conditions, sustainability reporting may exert more pronounced influence on reporting quality by reinforcing compliance and discouraging opportunistic behavior.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

A considerable body of research has examined the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management. Yet, the empirical findings remain heterogeneous across institutional settings, reporting regimes, and governance environments. Early studies in developed markets show that firms with higher-quality sustainability disclosures tend to exhibit lower levels of accrual-based and real earnings management, suggesting that greater transparency narrows managerial discretion and aligns reporting behavior with stakeholder expectations. Grimaldi et al. (2020) found that comprehensive ESG disclosure reduced both abnormal accruals and real activity manipulations in European firms and attributes to the decline to enhanced external monitoring and stronger normative pressures for responsible conduct. Dimitropoulos (2022) reported similar evidence across EU-listed companies, emphasizing how institutionalized sustainability practices reinforce financial reporting quality.

However, research in emerging markets yields more varied results. Several studies identify a negative association between sustainability reporting and earnings manipulation, reflecting improvements in reporting quality where sustainability frameworks are gaining traction. Trisnawati et al. (2016) found that Indonesian firms with extensive CSR disclosures exhibited significantly lower discretionary accruals, while Ayu (2020) demonstrated that voluntary social and environmental cost disclosures

curtailed opportunistic reporting. Nguyen (2024) investigated East Asian markets and argued that sustainability reporting enhances long-term monitoring and reduces managerial short-termism, contributing to sustained declines in earnings manipulation over time. These studies generally attribute the negative association to the incremental monitoring role of sustainability reporting within institutional environments that are strengthening their governance infrastructures.

Conversely, a parallel stream of literature argues that sustainability reporting may serve as a symbolic tool rather than a substantive governance mechanism, particularly in weak institutional environments. Ullah (2018) contended that firms may engage in sustainability disclosure as a legitimacy-enhancing strategy designed to divert stakeholder attention from financial reporting irregularities. Akhter (2017) identified patterns consistent with performance signaling rather than genuine accountability among Bangladeshi firms, raising concerns about greenwashing behavior. Ibrahim et al. (2015) reported mixed evidence from Malaysia, noting that certain CSR disclosure dimensions had no constraining effect on abnormal accruals, suggesting that the effectiveness of sustainability reporting as a governance device is contingent on institutional enforcement, stakeholder pressure, and the maturity of reporting frameworks.

More recently, scholars have highlighted the importance of ownership structure and political embeddedness in shaping the sustainability reporting–earnings management relationship. Studies from China and India reveal that SOEs often exhibit stronger sustainability disclosures but also encounter unique incentives to manipulate earnings to satisfy political, social, or bureaucratic objectives. Chinese SOEs have been shown to engage in sustainability reporting primarily to comply with political directives and maintain legitimacy in the eyes of government stakeholders (Cheng, 2025; Li et al., 2021). However, their earnings management practices vary depending on political cycles, regulatory scrutiny, and the intensity of government monitoring. Similar dynamics have been observed in Indian public-sector enterprises, where disclosure quality is influenced by both governance mandates and political expectations (Bhusan et al., 2024). These international findings emphasize the need to analyze sustainability reporting and financial reporting behavior jointly within SOEs, where legitimacy, institutional pressure, and agency conflicts converge in unique ways.

Despite this global interest, Bangladesh remains largely absent from the discourse. Existing Bangladeshi studies predominantly focus on CSR disclosures in private firms or explore earnings management in relation to governance mechanisms such as board structure, audit quality, and ownership concentration (Sobhan & Sharmin, 2024). Far fewer studies consider sustainability reporting as a holistic construct, and virtually none examine its interaction with earnings management in state-owned enterprises, entities that face distinctive pressures, including political oversight, public accountability requirements, and overlapping financial and social objectives (Rashid et al., 2024). Given the complexity of SOE mandates and the heightened societal expectations surrounding state-owned entities, the question of whether sustainability reporting serves as a monitoring tool or a symbolic signal remains empirically underexplored.

The literature suggests that the direction of the sustainability reporting–earnings management relationship is contingent on contextual forces: robust governance systems

and strong stakeholder scrutiny tend to reinforce the constraining effect of sustainability reporting, whereas weak enforcement and symbolic adoption can enable greenwashing. In SOEs, where both legitimacy pressures and institutional demands are higher than in private firms and where political costs of reputational failure may be substantial, the integrated theoretical perspective developed earlier suggests that sustainability reporting is more likely to operate as a substantive rather than symbolic mechanism. Therefore, drawing on the convergence of agency, legitimacy, stakeholder, and institutional perspectives, the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: Ceteris paribus, sustainability reporting is negatively and significantly associated with earnings management.

Research Methodology

Sample and Data

The study focuses on the manufacturing SOEs in Bangladesh, a sector that plays a pivotal role in driving industrial growth, generating employment, and contributing significantly to national revenue. At present, there are 49 non-financial SOEs in Bangladesh, of which 17 belong to the manufacturing sector and are listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). Given their strategic importance and visibility in the capital market, these firms constitute the population for this study. Data were collected from the annual reports and audited financial statements of the selected firms over a six-year period, covering 2018 to 2023 resulting a sample of 102 firm-years. The reason behind selecting 2018 as the starting year is the introduction of the Corporate Governance Code in 2018 which brought significant changes in the corporate governance systems of the listed firms of Bangladesh. The focus on manufacturing SOEs in Bangladesh allows the study to capture the dynamics of sustainability reporting and earnings management in a context where public accountability, political involvement, and economic contribution converge, making it particularly relevant for both theory and practice.

Definition of Variables

Dependent variable

To measure EM, the dependent variable of the study, discretionary accruals have been used. According to Park and Kwak (2007), managers tend to opt for discretionary accruals to manipulate earnings as such actions are less readily identifiable or discernible within financial reports. Excessive discretionary accruals may be perceived as indicative of opportunistic behavior (Dechow et al., 1995; Kothari et al., 2005). Discretionary accruals are measured using the absolute residuals obtained from the performance-adjusted modified Jones model. The model parameters and residuals are estimated separately for each year. This approach is adopted because the limited number of observations does not permit reliable coefficient estimation at the industry-year level. The model is as follows:

$$TA_t/A_{t-1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (1/A_{t-1}) + \beta_2 ((\Delta REV_t - \Delta REC_t)/A_{t-1}) + \beta_3 (PPE_t/A_{t-1}) + \beta_4 ROA_t + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where,

TA_t = Total accruals measured as the difference between net income and cash flow from operations per year.

A = Total assets

ΔREV = Changes in revenue

ΔREC = Changes in receivables

PPE = Property, plants and equipment

ROA = Return on assets

Independent Variable

As this study is empirical in nature, sustainability reporting was measured using the content analysis method, which is widely recognized for its ability to systematically classify and compare disclosure practices in an objective and quantitative manner. Specifically, the analysis covered the annual reports of 17 state-owned enterprises in the manufacturing sector of Bangladesh for the period 2018 to 2023. The content analysis employed an index-based approach, in which the presence or absence of specific disclosure items was examined using a binary coding scheme (assigning a score of 1 for the presence of a disclosure item and 0 for its absence). The aggregated scores across all disclosure items were then used to construct a sustainability reporting index for each firm-year observation (Gupta, 2021; Sobhan & Mia, 2024). Consistent with the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Standards, a total of 50 disclosure items were selected, covering environmental, social, and governance (ESG) dimensions. This index not only provides a standardized measure of sustainability reporting practices but also allows for meaningful comparison across firms and over time, thereby ensuring robustness and replicability in evaluating the extent of sustainability disclosures in Bangladeshi state-owned enterprises (Sobhan et al., 2025).

Control Variables

This study incorporates several control variables at the board and firm levels that are frequently linked to earnings management in prior literature. Board independence is included, as external directors are expected to mitigate managerial opportunism and reduce earnings manipulation (Aleqab & Ighnaim, 2021; Chekili, 2012). Board size is also controlled for, since larger boards generally enhance monitoring capacity and are associated with improved financial reporting quality (Hamid, 2019; Sukeecheep et al., 2013). Gender diversity on boards is considered given its mixed evidence, with some studies suggesting that female directors strengthen transparency while others report insignificant effects (Hili & Affess, 2012). Firm-specific controls include firm size, leverage, profitability, and firm age. Larger firms may have greater incentives to engage in earnings management to maintain market reputation (Gozali, 2021), while highly leveraged firms may manipulate earnings to meet debt covenants, though evidence is context-dependent (Gozali, 2021). Profitability, measured by return on assets (ROA), is included as profitable firms may either exhibit less earnings manipulation due to financial stability or more manipulation to sustain bonus-linked performance (Purnama &

Nurdiniah, 2018). Finally, firm age is considered, as both younger and older firms may face distinct incentives to manage earnings depending on competitive pressures and experience (Gozali, 2021; Hamzah et al., 2022). Table 1 presents the definition of variables used in the study.

Table 1: Definition of Variables

Variables	Symbol	Definition
Earning Management	EM	The absolute magnitude of the residuals obtained from the performance-adjusted Jones framework following Kothari et al. (2005).
Sustainability Reporting Index	SRI	Index value measured using content analysis. For details, please refer to section 4.2.2
Board Size	BSIZE	Natural logarithm of number of members in a board
Board Independence Ratio	BIND	Proportion of number of independent directors in a board to total board size
Board Gender Diversity	BGD	Proportion of number of female directors in a board to total board size
Firm Size	FSIZE	Natural logarithm of the company's total assets
Leverage	LEV	The ratio of total liabilities to total assets
Profitability	ROA	The ratio of profit before tax to total asset
Firm Age	FAGE	Natural logarithm of the difference between firm's listing year and present financial year

Research Model

To analyze the relationship between SRI and EM the following regression equation has been established:

$$EM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SRI_{it} + \beta_2 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_3 BIND_{it} + \beta_4 BGD_{it} + \beta_5 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_6 LEV_{it} + \beta_7 ROA_{it} + \beta_8 FAGE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Findings and Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables employed in this study, covering 102 firm-year observations of Bangladeshi manufacturing state-owned enterprises. The mean value of the earnings management (EM) variable is 0.0578, with a standard deviation of 0.0601, indicating moderate variation in discretionary accrual levels across firms. The Sustainability Reporting Index (SRI) has a mean score of 0.2855, suggesting relatively low levels of sustainability disclosure in the sample, which aligns with earlier findings that Bangladeshi firms, particularly SOEs, are less inclined to engage

in extensive ESG disclosure (Hossain et al., 2006). Board size (BSIZE) averages 9.62 members, and board independence (BIND) averages 32.57%, slightly above the minimum regulatory requirement, whereas board gender diversity (BGD) remains minimal at 3.97%, highlighting gender underrepresentation at the board level. Firms in the sample are, on average, large in size (mean total assets of BDT 51,736 million) but highly leveraged (mean leverage ratio of 0.9174). Profitability, measured by ROA, has a mean of -0.1258 , indicating that a considerable number of SOEs report losses during the study period. The average firm age is 26.94 years, reflecting the established nature of these enterprises.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
EM	102	0.0578	0.0601	0.0014	0.2322
SRI	102	0.2855	0.1054	0.0400	0.5000
BSIZE	102	9.6200	1.9080	6.0000	18.0000
BIND	102	0.3257	0.0628	0.2000	0.5000
BGD	102	0.0397	0.0546	0.0000	0.2000
FSIZE (in millions)	102	51736.12	80228.24	233.18	431868.05
LEV	102	0.9174	0.5280	0.0753	2.7914
ROA	102	-0.1258	0.4445	-2.3377	0.1897
FAGE	102	26.9400	12.0540	6.0000	46.0000

Figure 1 illustrates the year-wise trend of the Sustainability Reporting Index for the sampled firms. The figure shows modest but gradual improvement in sustainability disclosures over the study period, although overall SRI values remain low relative to international standards. This trend reflects the increasing influence of global reporting guidelines, such as those from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), and growing domestic awareness of ESG issues. However, the persistently low disclosure levels suggest that Bangladeshi SOEs may still be engaging in sustainability reporting primarily as a compliance exercise rather than as a strategic tool for stakeholder engagement, echoing earlier findings that such disclosures are often qualitative and limited in scope (Hossain et al., 2006; Rahman, 2020).

Figure 1: Year-wise Sustainability Reporting Index Values

Bivariate Analysis

Table 3 displays the Pearson correlation coefficients among the study variables. SRI is negatively and significantly correlated with EM (-0.2677 , $p < 0.05$), suggesting that higher sustainability reporting is associated with lower earnings management—consistent with prior research documenting the deterrent effect of ESG disclosures on opportunistic financial reporting (Dimitropoulos, 2022; Nguyen, 2024). Board independence (BIND) is positively correlated with EM, although insignificantly, while board size and firm size are both negatively correlated with EM. Leverage (LEV) exhibits a strong positive correlation with EM (0.4838 , $p < 0.05$), indicating that more leveraged firms may have greater incentives for earnings manipulation, aligning with the debt covenant hypothesis. Profitability (ROA) is negatively correlated with EM (-0.4017 , $p < 0.05$), consistent with evidence that more profitable firms are less likely to engage in earnings management (Fauzi & Sanusi, 2015). No multicollinearity concerns are indicated by the pairwise correlations, as none exceed the 0.80 threshold (Gujarati, 2003). The study also conducted a Cronbach’s alpha test and found a coefficient of 0.83, which indicates a high level of internal consistency and acceptable reliability of the measurement scale. This implies that the items used to construct the variable are reliably capturing the underlying construct.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	em	sri	bsize	bind	bgd	fsize	lev	roa	fage
em	1								
Sri	-0.2677*	1							
bsize	-0.1953	0.4283*	1						
bind	0.1129	-0.2745*	-0.3203*	1					
bgd	-0.1217	0.0142	0.1859	-0.3417*	1				
fsize	-0.2664*	0.6062*	0.6583*	-0.4280*	0.0957	1			
lev	0.4838*	-0.4303*	-0.3494*	0.3684*	-0.2164	-0.4556*	1		
roa	-0.4017*	0.4670*	0.4159*	-0.4377*	0.2477*	0.5179*	-0.6106*	1	
fage	-0.0329	-0.5180*	-0.3064*	0.1625	-0.1719	-0.5116*	0.0898	-0.1584	1

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$

Table 4 reports the variance inflation factors for all independent variables. The mean VIF is 2.3, with all values below the commonly accepted cut-off of 10, suggesting that multicollinearity is not a concern in the regression models (Wooldridge, 2016). The highest VIF is observed for ROA (3.72), followed by LEV (3.07) and firm size (2.96), all well within acceptable limits. This ensures the reliability and stability of the coefficient estimates in subsequent regression analyses.

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ROA	3.72	0.2688
LEV	3.07	0.3257

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
FSIZE	2.96	0.3378
SRI	2.38	0.4202
BSIZE	1.94	0.5155
FAGE	1.58	0.6329
BIND	1.49	0.6711
BGD	1.26	0.7937
Mean VIF	2.3	

Multivariate Analysis

Table V presents the results from both the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Fixed Effects (FE) regression models examining the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management. The selection of FE model was confirmed after conducting the Hausman test ($\chi^2 = 29.10$, $p = 0.0001$). In both models, SRI is negatively and significantly associated with EM (OLS: -0.2743 , $p < 0.05$; FE: -0.2197 , $p < 0.01$), confirming that greater sustainability disclosure reduces earnings management. This finding supports the predictions of agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) and legitimacy theory (Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975), as enhanced transparency through ESG reporting appears to curb managerial opportunism (Ayu, 2020; Trisnawati et al., 2016).

The difference in the magnitude of the SRI coefficients between the OLS and fixed effects models reflects their distinct estimation properties. While the OLS estimate captures both cross-sectional and time-series variation, the fixed effects model controls for unobserved, time-invariant firm-specific characteristics that may be correlated with sustainability reporting practices. Consequently, the smaller coefficient in the fixed effects model suggests that part of the association observed in the OLS estimation is driven by persistent firm-level traits, whereas the fixed effects estimate represents the more conservative within-firm effect of changes in sustainability reporting on earnings management over time.

Among the control variables, board size (BSIZE) and board independence (BIND) exhibit significant negative associations with EM, indicating that larger and more independent boards are effective in constraining earnings manipulation, in line with prior evidence from Nuryana and Surjandari (2019). Leverage (LEV) is positively and significantly related to EM, consistent with Ullah (2018), who found that financially pressured firms are more prone to manipulation. Profitability (ROA) shows a positive and significant relationship in the FE model, suggesting that profitable firms may still manage earnings to maintain performance trends—a nuance also observed in mixed findings from earlier literature (Ullah, 2018). Other variables, such as gender diversity (BGD), firm size (FSIZE), and firm age (FAGE), do not exhibit significant effects.

Table 5: Regression Results using OLS Model and Fixed Effects Model

Variable	Model 1 (OLS)		Model 2 (Fixed Effects)	
	Coef.	Std. Err	Coef.	Std. Err
SRI	-0.2743**	(0.9846)	-0.2197***	(0.9104)
BSIZE	-0.1041***	(1.2462)	-0.1127***	(1.1129)
BIND	-0.1028*	(1.5467)	-0.0946**	(1.3396)
BGD	-0.1104	(0.9441)	-0.0915	(0.9118)
FSIZE	-0.2035	(1.3319)	-0.1895	(1.0946)
LEV	0.0083***	(1.5946)	0.0076***	(1.4437)
ROA	0.0340	(0.0985)	0.0469*	(0.0887)
FAGE	-0.0202	(2.1247)	-0.0195	(1.9984)
CONSTANT	1.2617	(0.9867)	1.1149	(0.9121)
Year Effects	Yes		Yes	
Observations	102		102	
R-Squared	0.2808		0.2916	
F-Stat	13.51***		16.87***	

*p<0.10; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Discussion of the Findings

The empirical findings provide consistent evidence that sustainability reporting is associated with lower levels of earnings management in Bangladeshi manufacturing SOEs. The negative and statistically significant coefficient on the SRI across both OLS and fixed effects specifications suggests that firms engaging more extensively in sustainability disclosure exhibit higher financial reporting quality. Importantly, this association persists after controlling for firm-specific heterogeneity, indicating that the observed effect is not merely driven by time-invariant organizational characteristics.

From an agency-theoretic perspective, this finding implies that sustainability reporting functions as an effective monitoring mechanism in the SOE context. Enhanced ESG disclosure expands the information set available to government authorities, regulators, auditors, and the public, thereby reducing information asymmetry and limiting managerial discretion over financial reporting. Given the diffuse and politically mediated nature of ownership in SOEs, where traditional incentive alignment mechanisms are often weak, sustainability reporting may play a particularly salient governance role by increasing transparency and scrutiny. The results also carry important implications for legitimacy theory. SOEs are subject to heightened societal and political expectations due to their public ownership and strategic importance. Sustainability disclosures appear to strengthen organizational legitimacy by signaling compliance with social, environmental, and governance norms. In such settings, the reputational and political costs associated

with financial misreporting may outweigh the short-term benefits of earnings manipulation. This legitimacy-based explanation is especially relevant for loss-making or financially vulnerable SOEs, for which public scrutiny and political accountability tend to intensify. In these cases, sustainability reporting may serve as a credibility-enhancing mechanism that constrains opportunistic financial behavior rather than a symbolic façade.

The consistency of the findings with prior studies across both developed and emerging economies (Dimitropoulos, 2022; Grimaldi et al., 2020; Nguyen, 2024) suggests that the constraining effect of sustainability reporting on earnings management extends to public-sector enterprises operating in weaker institutional environments. However, the SOE-specific context amplifies the relevance of legitimacy and institutional pressures relative to purely market-based monitoring mechanisms observed in private firms. Unlike private corporations, SOEs face multidimensional accountability which increases the reputational risk of engaging in earnings manipulation when sustainability disclosures are visible.

Among the control variables, the negative association between board size, board independence, and earnings management indicates that stronger internal governance structures reinforce monitoring effectiveness in SOEs. Larger boards may provide a broader range of expertise and oversight capacity, while independent directors can mitigate political and managerial influence by strengthening objectivity in financial reporting oversight. These findings support the argument that internal governance mechanisms complement sustainability reporting in constraining managerial opportunism. The positive relationship between leverage and earnings management is consistent with the debt covenant hypothesis, suggesting that financially constrained SOEs may manipulate earnings to meet borrowing requirements or avoid regulatory intervention. This incentive may be particularly pronounced in SOEs that rely on government guarantees or subsidized financing, where deviations from expected performance could attract political scrutiny.

Profitability (ROA) exhibits a positive and significant association with earnings management in the fixed effects model. Rather than indicating weaker governance among profitable firms, this pattern may reflect income-smoothing behavior, whereby managers in consistently profitable SOEs engage in discretionary accruals to stabilize reported performance over time. In the SOE context, sustained profitability often carries implicit performance expectations from political principals, and managers may seek to avoid visible fluctuations that could trigger budget reallocations, policy interventions, or leadership changes. This finding aligns with behavioral agency theory, which suggests that managers respond asymmetrically to performance benchmarks and reference points, even in the absence of immediate financial distress.

Overall, the discussion highlights that sustainability reporting in Bangladeshi SOEs operates through intertwined agency, legitimacy, and institutional channels. Rather than serving merely symbolic purposes, sustainability disclosure appears to enhance accountability and constrain earnings manipulation, particularly in politically visible and socially accountable organizations. These findings underscore the importance of considering ownership structure and institutional context when evaluating the governance role of sustainability reporting in emerging economies.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between sustainability reporting and earnings management in the manufacturing state-owned enterprise (SOE) sector of Bangladesh. Drawing on both agency theory and legitimacy theory, the research argued that sustainability disclosures enhance transparency, accountability, and legitimacy, thereby reducing managers' incentives to engage in opportunistic accounting practices. Using a sample of SOEs and employing regression analysis, the findings revealed a significant negative association between sustainability reporting and earnings management. Specifically, firms that provided more extensive sustainability disclosures were less likely to manipulate earnings through discretionary accruals. Additionally, board characteristics such as independence and size were found to exert a constraining effect on earnings management, while leverage and profitability appeared to increase managers' incentives to manipulate financial outcomes. The results suggest that sustainability reporting functions as a valuable governance mechanism within SOEs, improving financial reporting quality and strengthening accountability to stakeholders.

The findings of this study have several policy-relevant and practice-oriented implications, particularly for regulators overseeing SOEs in Bangladesh. First, the evidence that sustainability reporting is associated with lower earnings management suggests that disclosure frameworks can function as an effective governance mechanism in politically embedded organizations. In this regard, regulatory authorities such as the Bangladesh Securities and Exchange Commission (BSEC) and relevant line ministries may consider mandating sustainability reporting for listed SOEs using internationally recognized standards such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). Beyond disclosure mandates, regulators could require external assurance of sustainability reports for SOEs, similar to financial statement audits, to enhance credibility and reduce symbolic or greenwashing-oriented reporting. Such measures would align SOE reporting practices with Bangladesh's commitments under the SDGs and Vision 2041. Second, the findings support a move toward integrated reporting for SOEs, whereby financial and non-financial information are disclosed in a unified reporting framework. Mandating integrated reporting would allow regulators and government principals to better evaluate how sustainability initiatives translate into financial outcomes, thereby improving accountability and performance monitoring. From a governance perspective, boards of SOEs should embed sustainability oversight within board committees such as audit or risk committees, rather than treating sustainability reporting as a peripheral compliance exercise. For institutional investors, development partners, and civil society stakeholders, the results suggest that sustainability disclosures can serve as a meaningful signal of reduced financial misreporting risk, particularly in public-sector enterprises subject to reputational and political scrutiny.

Despite these contributions, the study has several important limitations that warrant explicit acknowledgment. First, the analysis is restricted to listed manufacturing SOEs in Bangladesh, which limits the generalizability of the findings to unlisted SOEs, private firms, or service-oriented public enterprises. This sample restriction also introduces potential survivorship bias, as only SOEs that meet listing and continuity requirements are observed, possibly excluding poorly performing or restructured enterprises where earnings management dynamics may differ. Second, the relatively small number of listed

SOEs constrains the sample size, which may reduce statistical power and limit the ability to detect more nuanced effects. Third, the measurement of sustainability reporting relies on a manually constructed disclosure index, which captures the extent of disclosure but may be subject to measurement error and coder subjectivity, despite adherence to established coding procedures. The index does not fully reflect the credibility, depth, or assurance level of disclosed information. Fourth, earnings management is proxied using discretionary accruals, which may not adequately capture real earnings management practices such as overproduction or discretionary expense cuts.

These limitations open several specific and promising avenues for future research. First, scholars could conduct comparative analyses between SOEs and privately owned firms, or between listed and unlisted SOEs, to better isolate the role of ownership structure and political oversight. Second, future studies could explicitly examine moderating factors such as political connections, government subsidies, budget dependence, or external monitoring intensity to unpack the mechanisms through which sustainability reporting affects earnings management. Third, researchers could incorporate real earnings management measures alongside accrual-based proxies to capture a broader spectrum of managerial behavior. Fourth, the role of external assurance and integrated reporting adoption in strengthening the sustainability reporting–financial reporting quality link remains largely unexplored in emerging economies and represents a valuable extension. Finally, cross-country studies focusing on SOEs across comparable emerging markets could offer deeper insights into how institutional environments condition the effectiveness of sustainability reporting as a governance tool.

Declaration Statement

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References

- Akhter, T. (2017). Corporate Environmental Reporting and Profitability: A Study on Listed Companies in Bangladesh. *Jagannath University Journal of Business Studies*, 5(1–2), 99–114.
- Aleqab, M. M., & Ighnaim, M. M. (2021). The impact of board characteristics on earnings management. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, 10(3), 8. <https://doi.org/10.22495/JGRV10I3ART1>
- Ayu, M. L. G. (2020). The Impact of Environmental and Social Costs Disclosure on Financial Performance Mediating by Earning Management. *Polish Journal Of Management Studies*, 21(2).
- Bhusan, S., Dayanandan, A., & Naresh, G. (2024). Mandatory disclosure and bank earnings management in India. *Emerging Markets Review*, 62, 101187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EMEMAR.2024.101187>
- Chekili, S. (2012). Impact of Some Governance Mechanisms on Earnings Management:

An Empirical Validation Within the Tunisian Market. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 3(3), 95–104.

Cheng, L. (2025). Political governance and firm performance in China: Evidence from a quasi-natural experiment. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 76, 101348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFS.2024.101348>

Dechow, P., Sloan, R., & Sweeney, A. (1995). Detecting earnings management. *The Accounting Review*, 70(2), 193–225.

Deegan, C. (2002). Introduction The legitimising effect of social and environmental disclosures – a theoretical foundation. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15(3), 282–311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513570210435852>

DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48, 147–160. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101>

Dimitropoulos, P. E. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and earnings management in the EU: a panel data analysis approach. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 18(1), 68–84. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-04-2020-0156>

Dowling, J., & Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational legitimacy: Social values and organizational behavior. *Sociological Perspectives*, 18(1), 122–136. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1388226/ASSET/31FC6049-A88A-42FE-A23C-622FB5CA0D3A/ASSETS/1388226.FP.PNG>

Fauzi, F., & Sanusi, A. (2015). The Analysis of Effects of Voluntary Disclosure to the Relationship between Corporate Governance and Earnings Management. *International Conference On Information Technology And Business*.

Fernando, S., & Lawrence, S. (2014). A Theoretical Framework for CSR Practices: Integrating Legitimacy Theory, Stakeholder Theory and Institutional Theory. *Journal of Theoretical Accounting Research*, 10, 149–178.

Gozali, E. O. D. (2021). Firm Characteristics and Earnings Management in Listed Singaporean Corporations. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Kontemporer*, 13(2).

Grimaldi, F., Caragnano, A., Zito, M., & Mariani, M. (2020). Sustainability Engagement and Earnings Management: The Italian Context. *Sustainability* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 4881, 12(12), 4881. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12124881>

Gujarati, D. (2003). *Basic Econometrics*. McGraw-Hill Education.

Gupta, S. (2021). An Investigation into Sustainability Reporting Practices of BSE-500 Listed Companies in India: An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Management*. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Management*, 4(2), 152–158.

- Hamid, M. S. (2019). Impact Of Board Characteristics On Earning Management: A Study On Private Sectors In Malaysia. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies*, 6(1).
- Hamzah, R. S., Octavina, E., & Khamisah, N. (2022). Examining Earnings Management and Firm Age: A Quantitative Comparative Study. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Kontemporer*, 14(1), 32–40.
- Hili, W., & Affess, H. (2012). Corporate Boards Gender Diversity and Earnings Persistence: The Case of French Listed Firms. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 12(22), 64–72.
- Hossain, M., Islam, K., & Andrew, J. (2006). Corporate Social and Environmental Disclosure in Developing Countries: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Asian Pacific Conference on International Accounting Issues*, 1–22.
- Ibrahim, M. S., Darus, F., Yusoff, H., & Muhamad, R. (2015). Analysis of Earnings Management Practices and Sustainability Reporting for Corporations that Offer Islamic Products & Services. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 28, 176–182. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)01098-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)01098-9)
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976a). Also published in Foundations of Organizational Strategy. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 4, 305–360.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976b). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)
- Khan, M. A. (2021). Performance Analysis of Nonfinancial State-Owned Enterprises In Bangladesh. *A Contemporary Business Journal*, 10(1).
- Kothari, S. P., Leone, A. J., & Wasley, C. E. (2005). Performance matched discretionary accrual measures. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 39(1), 163–197.
- Li, L., Monroe, G. S., & Wang, J. J. (2021). State ownership and abnormal accruals in highly-valued firms: Evidence from China. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 17(1), 100223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCAE.2020.100223>
- Mnif Sellami, Y., Dammak Ben Hlima, N., & Jarboui, A. (2019). An empirical investigation of determinants of sustainability report assurance in France. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 17(2), 320–342. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-02-2018-0019>
- Nguyen, L. T. (2024). The relationship between corporate sustainability performance and earnings management: evidence from emerging East Asian economies. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 22(3), 564–582. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-09-2021-0302>

- Nuryana, Y., & Surjandari, D. A. (2019). The Effect of Good Corporate Governance Mechanism, and Earning Management on Company Financial Performance. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 19(1), 27–39.
- Onoja, A. A., Okoye, E. I., & Nwoye, U. J. (2021). Global Reporting Initiative and Sustainability Reporting Practices: A Study of Nigeria and South Africa Oil and Gas Firms. *Research Journal of Management Practice*, 1(12), 1–14.
- Park, J. I., & Kwak, S. K. (2007). Auditor changes and audit quality. *Study on Accounting, Taxation and Auditing*, 46, 191–226.
- Purnama, I., & Nurdiniah, D. (2018). Profitability, Firm Size, and Earnings Management: the Moderating Effect of Managerial Ownership. *5th Annual International Conference on Accounting Research*.
- Rahman, M. (2020). Moderating Effect of Earnings Management in the Relationship between Sustainability Reporting Initiatives and Value Relevance. *Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 4(266–277).
- Rashid, M. H. U., Begum, F., Hossain, S. Z., & Said, J. (2024). Does CSR affect tax avoidance? Moderating role of political connections in Bangladesh banking sector. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 20(4), 719–739.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-09-2022-0364>
- Sobhan, R., & Mia, M. R. (2024). Impact of board characteristics on integrated reporting: evidence from South Asian countries. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting, ahead-of-print*(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-07-2023-0363/FULL/XML>
- Sobhan, R., & Sharmin, T. (2024). Examining the Nexus between Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Earnings Management: Evidence from the State-owned Enterprises of Bangladesh. *Journal of Business, Economics and Finance*, 13(1), 24–36. <https://doi.org/0.17261/Pressacademia.2024.1899>
- Sobhan, R., Shohan, M. M. R., & Uddin, S. I. (2025). Environmental reporting and financial performance: the role of board independence. *Journal of Accounting & Organizational Change, ahead-of-print*(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-05-2024-0149>
- Sukeecheep, S., Yarram, S. R., & Farooque, O. A. (2013). Earnings Management and Board Characteristics in Thai Listed Companies. *The 2013 IBEA, International Conference on Business, Economics, and Accounting*.
- Trisnawati, R., Wiyadi, & Setiawati, E. (2016). Sustainability Reporting and Earning Management (Empirical Studies in the companies that participated in the Indonesian Sustainability Reporting Award (ISRA)). *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 11(1), 11–16.
- Ullah, S. (2018). Corporate Environmental Disclosure and Earnings Quality: Evidence

from Malaysian Firms. *Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 2(2).

Wooldridge, J. M. (2016). *Introductory Econometrics* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.

Zogning, F. (2017). Agency Theory: A Critical Review. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(2).

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